

UCH O‘LCHAMLI FOKKER-PLANK TENGLAMASINI BIR O‘LCHAMLI FOKKER-PLANK TENGLAMASIGA KELTIRISH

Boltayeva Go‘zal Komilovna

Urganch RANCH texnologiya universiteti o‘qituvchisi

boltayevagozal@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Maqolada xususiy hosilali giperbolik tipdagi differensial tenglamani Mathcad va MATLAB matematik redaktorlari yordamida sonli yechish yo‘llari keltirilgan. Bir qator misollarning yechilishi hamda olingan natijalar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: xususiy hosila, giperbolik tip, chekli ayirma, to‘r funksiyasi, vaqt, Nyuton usuli, silliq yechim, Fokker – Plank tenglamasi, zarrachalar oqimi, burchak.

Aytaylik, $\Omega \subset R$ fazoviy soha bo‘lsin. Agar ψ funksiya faqat $x_3 = z$ bo‘lganda

$x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ ga bog‘liq bo‘lsa, u holda $\omega \cdot \nabla \psi = \omega_3 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}$ o‘rinli bo‘lib, bu had

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \omega \cdot \nabla \psi + \alpha \psi = \sigma \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1 - \mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right] + \frac{1}{1 - \mu^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} \right\} + \frac{\partial (S_M \psi)}{\partial e} + W$$

tenglamaning birinchi hadiga mos keladi, bunda $\mu = \omega_3$. Oldin faraz qilganimizdek, agar fazoviy soha $\Omega = \Omega^* \times (Z_{ini}, Z_{fin}), \Omega^* \subset R^2$ (1.1 – rasm) ko‘rinishda bo‘lsa, u holda masala bir o‘lchamli plastinada qo‘yiladi. Bunda asosiy g‘oya shundan iboratki, quyidagi sabablarga ko‘ra fazoviy o‘zgaruvchilar 3 tadan 1 taga kamayadi:

1.1-rasm: Bir o‘lchamli plastina. Bu uch o‘lchamli sohaning maxsus turi bo‘ladi.

- ψ funksiya χ_1 yoki χ_2 qiymatda o‘zgarmaydi;
- soha bir o‘lchamli (Z_{ini}, Z_{fin}) sohaning nuqtalari to‘plamidan iborat.

1.2-§. Furye usuli.

$$\psi_{\{(\theta=0)\}} \equiv \psi_{\{(\theta=2\pi)\}}, \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right)_{\{(\theta=0)\}} \equiv \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right)_{\{(\theta=2\pi)\}}, \text{ davriylik shartlari Furye usuli}$$

yorda-mida

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \omega \cdot \nabla \psi + \alpha \psi = \sigma \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1 - \mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right] + \frac{1}{1 - \mu^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} \right\} + \frac{\partial (S_M \psi)}{\partial e} + W \quad \psi_{\{(\epsilon=\infty)\}} \equiv 0$$

masalani θ – erkli masalalar to‘plamiga keltirish imkonini beradi.

Faraz qilaylik, oqimning burchak tezligi Furye qatori yordamida quyidagicha

$$\psi(x, t, \mu, \theta, \epsilon) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_k(x, t, \mu, \epsilon) e^{ik\theta}, \quad [1.2.1]$$

ifodalansin, bunda koeffitsientlar

$$\psi_k(x, t, \mu, \epsilon) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \psi(x, t, \mu, \theta, \epsilon) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta, \quad [1.2.2]$$

tenglik orqali aniqlanadi.

Agar $\psi(x, t, \mu, \theta, \epsilon) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_k(x, t, \mu, \epsilon) e^{ik\theta}$, dagi qator tez yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lsa,

u holda ψ_k koeffitsientlarning bir nechtasi ma’lum bo‘lgan holda ψ yechimni aniqlash mumkin. Shuning uchun, ψ_k Furye koeffitsientlari qaysi tenglamani qanoatlantirishini o‘rganamiz.

Berilgan G funksiya uchun uning θ o‘zgaruvchi bo‘yicha k –Furye koeffitsientini G_k orqali belgilaymiz.

$$\text{Dastlab, } \psi_k(x, t, \mu, \epsilon) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \psi(x, t, \mu, \theta, \epsilon) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta, \quad \text{tenglamaga asosan,}$$

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \omega \cdot \nabla \psi + \alpha \psi = \sigma \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1 - \mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right] + \frac{1}{1 - \mu^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} \right\} + \frac{\partial (S_M \psi)}{\partial \epsilon} + W$$

tenglamadagi har bir hadni $e^{-ik\theta}$ ga ko‘paytirib, $\theta = 0$ dan $\theta = 2\pi$ gacha integrallaymiz va 2π ga bo‘lamiz. α yoki σ ning birortasi ham θ ga bog‘liq bo‘lmasin deb faraz qilamiz. U holda natijalar quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial t}, \quad [1.2.3]$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\omega \cdot \nabla \psi) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \mu^2}}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial (\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial (\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_2} \right\} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3},$$

[1.2.4]

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \alpha \psi e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \alpha \psi_k, \quad [1.2.5]$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left\{ (1 - \mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right\} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1 - \mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial \mu} \right], \quad [1.2.6]$$

$$0 \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sigma}{1 - \mu^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = -\frac{\sigma k^2}{1 - \mu^2} \psi_k, \quad [1.2.7]$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\partial (S_M \psi)}{\partial \epsilon} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{\partial (S_M \psi_k)}{\partial \epsilon}, \quad [1.2.8]$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} W e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = W_k, \quad [1.2.9]$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\omega \cdot \nabla \psi) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \mu^2}}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial (\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial (\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_2} \right\} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3},$$

tenglamani hosil qilish qiyin bo‘lganligi uchun bu jarayonni batafsil o‘rganamiz.

Dastlab, $\omega = \omega(\varphi, \theta) = (\sin \varphi \cos \theta, \sin \varphi \sin \theta, \cos \varphi)$, tenglamani e'tiborga olish zarur. U holda

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\omega \cdot \nabla \psi) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ \int_0^{2\pi} \sin \varphi \cos \theta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_1} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta + \int_0^{2\pi} \sin \varphi \sin \theta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_2} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta + \int_0^{2\pi} \cos \varphi \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_3} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta \right\}. [1.2.10]$$

bo'ladi. Ohirgi tenglamadagi uchinchi qo'shiluvchi $\mu = \cos \varphi$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\omega \cdot \nabla \psi) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{\sqrt{1-\mu^2}}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_2} \right\} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3},$$

tenglamadagi $\mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3}$ hadni beradi; shuningdek $\sin \varphi = \sqrt{1-\mu^2}$ had esa huddi shu

tenglikning bosh qismini beradi. Va nihoyat ushbu

$$\left[(\cos \theta) \psi \right]_k = \frac{1}{2} (\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1}) \quad [1.2.11]$$

$$\left[(\sin \theta) \psi \right]_k = \frac{1}{2} (\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1}) \quad [1.2.12]$$

tengliklar

orqali

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\omega \cdot \nabla \psi) e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{\sqrt{1-\mu^2}}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_2} \right\} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3},$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Ohirgi $\left[(\cos \theta) \psi \right]_k = \frac{1}{2} (\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})$ va

$\left[(\sin \theta) \psi \right]_k = \frac{1}{2} (\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})$ tengliklarni bevosita hisoblash yoki Furiye qatori

ko'paytmasini hisoblash orqali tekshirish mumkin.

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sigma}{1-\mu^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = -\frac{\sigma k^2}{1-\mu^2} \psi_k, \text{ tenglama ikki marta bo'laklab integrallash}$$

hamda $\psi_{\{(\theta=0)\}} \equiv \psi_{\{(\theta=2\pi)\}}, \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right)_{\{(\theta=0)\}} \equiv \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right)_{\{(\theta=2\pi)\}}$, davriy shartlar yordamida hosil

qilingan. Haqiqatdan,

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right)_{\{\theta=2\pi\}} - \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right)_{\{\theta=0\}} +$$

$$ik \left(\psi_{\{\theta=2\pi\}} - \psi_{\{\theta=0\}} \right) - k^2 \int_0^{2\pi} \psi e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = -k^2 \int_0^{2\pi} \psi e^{-ik\theta} d\theta \quad [1.2.13]$$

Qolgan $\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial t}$, $\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} W e^{-ik\theta} d\theta = W_k$, tenglamalar trivial

bo‘ladi. Endi olingan barcha natijalarni qo‘shib,

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial t} + \frac{\sqrt{1-\mu^2}}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_2} \right\} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3} + \left(\alpha + \frac{\sigma k^2}{1-\mu^2} \right) \psi_k =$$

$$\sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1-\mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial \mu} \right] + \frac{\partial(S_M \psi)}{\partial \epsilon} + W_k. \quad [1.2.14]$$

bo‘lishini topamiz.

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial t} + \frac{\sqrt{1-\mu^2}}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} + \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial(\psi_{k+1} - \psi_{k-1})}{\partial x_2} \right\} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3} + \left(\alpha + \frac{\sigma k^2}{1-\mu^2} \right) \psi_k =$$

$$\sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1-\mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial \mu} \right] + \frac{\partial(S_M \psi)}{\partial \epsilon} + W_k. \quad \text{tenglama orqali beriluvchi masala}$$

noma’lum bo‘lgan ψ_{k-1} va ψ_{k+1} yopilmalarni talab qiladi. Bir nechta $\psi_{k-m}, \dots, \psi_{k+m}$ noma’lumli sistemani qarash ham, ψ_{k-m} va ψ_{k+m} yopilmalar zarur bo‘ladi. Bunda ψ funksiya x_1 ga ham x_2 ga ham bog‘liq bo‘lmagan holda ψ_k uchun yagona yechimga ega bo‘lar edik.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, agar ψ funksiya x_3 orqali x ga ham bog‘liq bo‘lsa, bundan tashqari α yoki σ ning birortasi θ ga bog‘liq bo‘lmasa, u holda Furrye usuli yordamida θ bog‘liqlikni bartaraf etish mumkin. Yuqoridagilarni inobatga olib, har bir ψ_k Furrye koeffitsienti

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial t} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial x_3} + \left(\alpha + \frac{\sigma k^2}{1-\mu^2} \right) \psi_k = \sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[(1-\mu^2) \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial \mu} \right] + \frac{\partial(S_M \psi)}{\partial \epsilon} + W_k.$$

[1.2.15]

quyidagi

$$(\psi_k)_{\{t=T_{ini}\}} \equiv \psi \quad [1.2.16]$$

$$(\psi_k)_{\{(x,\omega) \in \partial\Omega \times S^2: \omega \cdot n(x) < 0\}} \equiv F_k \quad [1.2.17]$$

$$(\psi_k)_{\{\epsilon=\infty\}} \equiv 0 \quad [1.2.18] \text{ shartlarni qanoatlantiradi.}$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Aziz, A. Kadir; French, Donald A.; Jensen, Soren and Kellogg, Royal Bruce. Origins, analysis and numerical approximation of a forward-backward parabolic problem, *Mathematical Modelling and Numerical Analysis*, **33**, № 5, 1999, 895-922.
2. Bartine, David Elliott. *Low-energy Electron Transport by the Method of Discrete Ordinates*. Ph.D thesis, University of Missouri-Rolla (now Missouri University of Science and Technology), 1971.
3. Beals, Richard. On an equation of mixed type from electron scattering theory, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 58 № 1 (1977) 32-45.
4. BEALS, Richard. Indefinite Sturm-Liouville problems and half range completeness, *Journal of Differential Equation* 56 № 3 (1985) 391-407.
5. Davis, Timothy A. (2006) *Direct Methods for Sparse Linear Systems*. SIAM, Philadelphia, PA.